

Coconut Shells as the Alternative Equipment for Foot Reflexology

Authors : Nichanant Sermsri, Chananchida Yuktirat

Abstract : This research was the experimental research. Its purpose was to find out how coconut shells can be adapted to be equipment for foot and calf reflexology. The sample group was 58 female street vendors in Thewet Market, Dusit District, Bangkok, selected by selection criteria and voluntary. The data collecting tool in this research was the Visual Analogue Scale. The massaging tool made from coconut shells (designed and produced by the research team) was the key equipment for this research. The duration of the research was 1 month. The research team assessed the level of exhaustion and heart rate among sample group before and after the massage, then analyzed the data by mean, standard deviation and paired sample t-test. We found out from the research that 1) The level of exhaustion decreased 4.529 levels after the massage. The standard deviation was 1.6195. The heart rates went down 11.67 times/minute. The standard deviation was 6.742. 2) The level of exhaustion and heart rate after the massage decreased with the statistically significance at 0.01.

Keywords : foot reflexology, massaging plate, coconut shells, ecological sciences

Conference Title : ICEBESE 2014 : International Conference on Environmental, Biological, Ecological Sciences and Engineering

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : April 28-29, 2014